

Titrimetric Determination of Iron(III), Molybdenum(VI) and Vanadium(V) after Reduction with Aluminium Amalgam[@]

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Use of aluminium amalgam as a reducing agent is investigated with a view to its applications to the estimation of iron(III), molybdenum(VI) and vanadium(V). The pieces of aluminium metal are lightly coated with mercury by treatment with mercuric chloride solution and are used in dil. HCl or dil. H₂SO₄ for iron(III), molybdenum(VI) and vanadium(V). The process requires 10 to 15 minutes and the reduction to the lower state is quantitative. The aluminium metal is cheaper than either zinc or silver. This procedure is simple and can be profitably adopted for routine estimations. Interference caused by some commonly associated ions is investigated.

SEVERAL metals can be estimated by reducing them to lower oxidation states by using zinc metal in a Jones reductor. The rates of reduction of iron(III), molybdenum(VI), vanadium(V), titanium(IV), chromium(III), niobium(V) were increased by using zinc amalgam instead of zinc¹. It was found that by the time 2 per cent. of the zinc has been consumed the reduction becomes too slow to be of any practical value². Riegel and Schwartz also found that the zinc amalgam method was inconvenient. They suggested the use of aluminium powder to reduce iron³ and molybdenum⁴. However aluminium powder is inconvenient as it needs special preparation. Methods in which various other forms of pure aluminium metal such as aluminium foils are used for reduction of iron have also been investigated⁵. Estimation of ferric iron by silver reductor was studied by Walden, Hammet and Edmond⁶; Henry and Gelbach⁶. Birnbaum and Walden⁷ used the silver reductor for the molybdenum(VI). Although silver has high reducing power in high acidic medium, it is commercially unsuitable. An attempt has been made to reduce vanadium(V) to vanadium(III) by mercury reductor in hydrochloric acid medium⁸, however it is incapable of reducing vanadium(V) to vanadium(III) in sulphuric acid medium. This reductor doesn't reduce vanadium(V) to vanadium(II).

In the present work the authors found that aluminium amalgam is more suitable than any other previously reported reducing agent for iron, molybdenum and vanadium.

Experimental

Materials

All chemicals used were A.R. grade and glass distilled water was used throughout.

0.01 N Potassium Permanganate

Dissolve 0.158 g of potassium permanganate to give 500 ml solution and standardize with ferrous ammonium sulphate⁹.

Iron(III) Solution

Dissolve 10.760 g of ferric ammonium sulphate crystals to give 100 ml solution. And 5 ml dilute sulphuric acid before dilution. An aliquot is reduced with SnCl₂ and the resulting ferrous iron is estimated with permanganate⁹.

Molybdenum(VI) Solution

Dissolve 2.300 g of ammonium molybdate in water to give 100 ml solution and standardize by iodometric reduction method¹⁰.

Vanadium(V) Solution

Dissolve 2.868 g of ammonium meta-vanadate in water to give 100 ml solution and standardize by potassium iodate method⁹.

Amalgamated Aluminium

Treat 5 mm × 5 mm pieces of 1 mm thick sheet of iron-free aluminium with 5% solution of mercuric chloride for 5-10 minutes and wash thoroughly with distilled water. The same solution of HgCl₂ can be repeatedly used several times.

Apparatus

Jones reductor is a 12 cm diameter, 22 cm long column with a stopcock at one end.

Procedure

(a) Reduction of iron(III) to iron(II) :

Transfer an aliquot of solution containing about 8-10 mg of iron to the reductor column, acidifying

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the solution with 5*N* sulphuric acid or 5*N* hydrochloric acid to give the acidity 0.5*N* and 0.25*N* respectively in the final volume of 25 ml. Wait for 10-15 minutes and then titrate the reduced iron(II) solution against 0.01 *N* potassium permanganate.

(b) *Reduction of molybdenum(VI) to molybdenum(III)* :

Transfer an aliquot of the solution containing 8-10 mg of molybdenum(VI) as ammonium molybdate solution to the reductor column, acidifying with exact quantity of 5*N* sulphuric acid or 5*N* hydrochloric acid to give acidity 0.5*N* and 0.25*N* respectively in the final volume of 25 ml. Wait for 10-15 minutes and then collect the reduced solution along with water washings in a conical flask containing excess of acidified ferric alum and 5 ml of syrupy phosphoric acid⁹ to avoid air oxidation of molybdenum(III). Titrate the contents against 0.01*N* potassium permanganate.

(c) *Reduction of vanadium(V) to vanadium(II)*

Transfer an aliquot of the solution containing 8-10 mg of vanadium(V) as ammonium meta-vanadate solution to the reductor column, acidifying with exact quantity of 5*N* sulphuric acid or 5*N* hydrochloric acid to give acidity 0.5*N* and 0.25*N* respectively in the final volume of 25 ml. Wait for 10-15 minutes to complete the reduction. The progress of the reduction can be seen from the colour changes (viz. yellow-blue-green-violet). Vanadium(V) forms VO_2^+ ions of yellow colour in acid medium. On reduction the vanadium(IV) ion is first produced in the form of aquovanadyl $[\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ of blue colour. Further the vanadium(III) is produced in the form of aquo ions $[\text{V}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{3+}$ of green colour. Finally the vanadium(II) ion is produced in the form of aquo ions $[\text{V}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ of violet colour. If the ions $[\text{V}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$ and $\text{VO}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ are simultaneously present in the solution, an intermediate compound of brown colour, that has the bridged group $[\text{VOV}]^{4+}$ is formed and there is brownish hue which latter on changes to violet. Collect the reduced solution along with water washings in a conical flask containing excess of acidified ferric solution and 5 ml of syrupy phosphoric acid to avoid air oxidation of vanadium¹¹(II). Titrate the contents against 0.01*N* potassium permanganate.

Results and Discussion

It is observed that reduction with aluminium amalgam is possible only in acidic medium, particularly between the acidity range of 0.5 to 2.5*N* for sulphuric acid and 0.25 to 2.0*N* for hydrochloric acid. Above this concentration reaction is vigorous and difficult to control. Sometimes the contents of the column are spirted out.

The rate of reduction directly corresponds to the acidity of the solution particularly in hydrochloric acid solution. In hydrochloric acid medium the potential of $\text{Hg}_2\text{Cl}_2/\text{Hg}$ couple decreases, so the

efficiency of the reductor increases. Quantitative reduction of iron(III), molybdenum(VI) and vanadium(V) to iron(II), molybdenum(III) and vanadium(II) is possible by this reductor even at low acidity due to great difference in the standard redox potential of the reductant and oxidant systems.

The quantitative nature of the vanadium(V) reduction is confirmed by comparing the absorption spectra of vanadium(III) produced from mercury reductor in hydrochloric acid medium⁶ and vanadium(III) produced by this method. Both of these have absorption maxima at 420 nm and 600 nm. Identical nature of the spectra shows quantitative reduction of vanadium(V) to vanadium(III) state by aluminium amalgam. Spectral characteristics of vanadium(IV) obtained by oxidation of vanadium(III) is in agreement with the spectral characteristics of vanadium(IV) obtained by mercury reductor in sulphuric acid medium⁶ (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1 : Absorption spectra of 0.021*M* solution of Vanadium(III) and Vanadium(IV)

Vanadium (III) : -○- = Mercury reductor method ;
 -●- = Aluminium amalgam method.
 Vanadium (IV) : -□- = Mercury reductor method ;
 -■- = Aluminium amalgam method.

The present method for the determination of vanadium is more convenient when compared with earlier reported methods.

Reactivity of aluminium amalgam increases with time and evolution of hydrogen becomes rapid¹². The reaction with water is exothermic, heat liberated keeps the solution hot and it speeds up the reaction. Results obtained are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Silver reductor process is commercially unsuitable due to the high cost of silver metal, though the reduction can be carried out at the HCl molarity range of 0.5 to 1.5. Aluminium powder procedure for iron and molybdenum is inconvenient as it requires special preparation of powder and heating of the solution is also essential along with high

TABLE—1 REDUCTION OF Fe(III) TO Fe(II) AND FURTHER PERMANGANOMETRIC DETERMINATION

Iron(III) taken mg	Iron(II) found mg	Standard deviation of 5 observations
10.05	10.05	±0.010
19.50	19.51	±0.011
45.00	44.96	±0.013
62.20	62.15	±0.020

TABLE—2 REDUCTION OF Mo(VI) TO Mo(III) AND FURTHER PERMANGANOMETRIC DETERMINATION

Molybdenum(VI) taken mg	Molybdenum(III) found mg	Standard deviation of 5 observations
9.53	9.508	±0.028
25.00	25.05	±0.017
42.20	42.25	±0.019
50.00	49.96	±0.015

TABLE—3 REDUCTION OF V(V) TO V(II), SUBSEQUENT REDUCTION OF Fe(III) TO Fe(II) AND PERMANGANOMETRIC DETERMINATION

Vanadium(V) taken mg	Vanadium(II) found mg	Standard deviation of 5 observations
7.22	7.20	±0.030
28.56	28.60	±0.021
50.25	50.30	±0.018
60.10	60.07	±0.015

acidity ranges. Mercury reductor is also incapable of reducing vanadium(V) to vanadium(III) in either sulphuric or hydrochloric acid medium⁸.

Sulphate, acetate and perchlorate ions do not interfere in this method. Phosphate and nitrate ions in low concentrations do not interfere, however, in higher concentration they give erroneous results. The interferences of these ions were studied using corresponding acids. Zn^{2+} , Cd^{2+} , Bi^{3+} , Be^{3+} and Mg^{2+} do not interfere, however ions such as Tl^{4+} , As^{5+} and W^{6+} interfere strongly and must be absent.

Aluminium amalgam reduces ions chosen for the present study in 0.25N HCl or 0.5N H_2SO_4 . It

works efficiently and more rapidly than any of the hitherto used reductors. It is also cheaper than zinc, mercury or silver. However the amalgam reacts with water and hence it should be prepared just before use. The column should be emptied immediately after use, otherwise the product of the reaction with water (i.e., Aluminium, hydroxide) occupies more volume and hence the column breaks. The used amalgam may be washed free of acid with distilled water, blotted with filter paper and stored in a stoppered bottle for further use.

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